

Effect of blue-green algae (BGA) on rice yield

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We conducted a field trial in clay loam soil in 1979, 1980, and 1981 wet seasons at Raipur to determine the N contribution of BGA in lowland rice dwarf variety K35-2752. Soil characteristics were as follows: pH, 7.8; organic carbon, 0.7%; and available N, P₂O₅, and K₂O, 0.01, 0.0016, and 0.018%. Treatments were in randomized block design with four replications. N was applied in 3 splits (1/4 basal, 1/2 at tillering, and 1/4 at panicle initiation), and 26

Effect of BGA and N level on rice yield, Raipur, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		
	1979	1980	1981
Control	3.0	2.7	2.0
25 kg N/ha	3.5	3.4	2.5
50 kg N/ha	4.4	3.8	2.8
75 kg N/ha	4.7	4.2	3.2
10 kg dried BGA/ha	3.6	3.3	2.2
10 kg dried BCA + 25 kg N/ha	3.7	3.5	2.4
LSD (5%)	0.62	0.37	0.28

kg P and 33 kg K/ha were applied basally to all treatments. BGA inoculum was from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project. Visual observations of BGA development were not recorded. Yield component was recorded.

BGA inoculation and N level significantly affected yield. Rice yield increased with N level from 25 to 75

kg N/ha. Application of 10 kg BGA/ha gave significantly higher yield over the control in 1979 and 1980. In 1981, heavy rains fell immediately after BGA inoculation, and reduced effect on yield (see table). Inoculation of 10 kg dried BGA/ha produced rice yield equivalent to that with 25 kg N/ha. □

Effect of fertilizer rate on yield of rice cultivars

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Yield of Nipponbare, which averages 4.5 to 4.6 t/ha in northern Hyogo Prefecture, was compared to that of Milyang 23, Swong 258, and Chugoku 91 in different fertilizer treatments. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 30 × 15-cm spacing and 3-5 seedlings/hill on 10 May, in a split-plot design with 2 replications.

Soil was a sandy clay loam with pH 6.8 (H₂O 1:5), EC 130 μS/cm, 4.0% organic matter, 0.16% total N, 2.32% total organic carbon, 17.0 mg/100 g available P (Bray-Kurtz No. 2 method), 16.9 meq/100 g CEC (1N-CaCl₂, pH = 8.2), and exchangeable cations 0.10 meq/100 g Na, 0.22 meq/100 g K, 9.67 meq/100 g Ca, 1.37 meq/100 g Mg, and 0.01 meq/100 g Al (1N-CH₃COONH₄).

In control plots, fertilizer was applied basally at 40, 29, and 40 kg NPK/ha and topdressed at 20, 14.3,

Effect of fertilizer rate on grain yield and yield components of 4 rice cultivars, Hyogo Prefecture, Japan.

Cultivar	Treatment plot	Top dry wt (t/ha)	Yield component				Grain ^b yield (t/ha)	Relative increase of grain yield (%) ^c
			Panicle (no./m ²)	1000-grain wt (g)	Ripening ^a (%)	Grains (no./panicle)		
Nipponbare	Control	15.4	420	22.6	95	62	5.5	19
	Treated	18.7	502	22.0	93	65	6.6	
Milyang 23	Control	11.4	326	23.3	85	66	4.1	-14
	Treated	14.5	378	23.3	81	50	3.6	
Swong 258	Control	14.2	389	22.5	92	69	5.5	17
	Treated	16.2	451	22.5	91	70	6.4	
Chugoku 91	Control	14.4	325	21.2	87	98	5.9	11
	Treated	16.3	388	20.2	76	111	6.5	
Source of variation ^d								
Cultivar (C)		**	**	**	**	**	**	
Fertilizer (F)		**	**	ns	**	ns	**	
C × F		ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	**	

^a Ripening (%) = no. filled grain × 100/(no. filled grain + no. unfilled grain), ^b Grain yield (t/ha) = panicle no./m² × 1000-grain weight (g) × ripening (%) × grain no./panicle/10⁷. ^c Relative increase of grain yield (%) = (grain yield of T - grain yield of C) × 100/grain yield of C, where T and C are additional fertilizer treatment plot and control plot. ^d** = significant at 1% level, ns = not significant.

and 20 kg NPK/ha at active tillering, panicle initiation, and reduction division and heading. Treated plots received 1.5 times more fertilizer at all stages except at heading, when an equal amount of fertilizer was applied to all plots. Total fertilizer applied was 120, 86, and 120 kg NPK/ha to control plots and 170, 122, and 170 kg NPK/ha to treated plots.

Top dry weight, yield components, and grain yield differed significantly among four rice cultivars and treatments (see table). Panicle number increased more than ripening percentage decreased; the result was increased grain yield. Fertilizer increased grain yield about 16% in all cultivars except Milyang 23, which was badly affected by a typhoon. □